

Involvement and communication with citizens about waste

Charlotte Harritshøj Frausing and Maria Jeanine Annel

DTU Environment, Technical University of Denmark

INTRODUCTION

As focus on waste sorting and recycling of materials increases it is important to encourage citizens to participate and sort the waste in their house. This project will through a qualitative analysis analyse how mediation in sorting household waste is as tailored to the individual citizen as possible. Our partner is Miljøpunkt Nørrebro and the user group for the studies is citizens of Wesselsgade.

THEORY

Human behaviour is investigated in order to understand the motives and motivations resulting in citizen action. For the study of communication and motivation, key words are: citizen involvement, theories of learning and learning styles, and the "myth of information". It is assumed that motivation for sorting waste is divided into three categories: emotion, intellect and instinct. Involvement of citizens and the individual role is an important key to understanding how to address information regarding sorting and handling of waste.

METHODS

A series of interviews in the user group are performed and then analysed. Thereby the differences in information and involvement between the two sides of the street are discovered. The even-numbered side of the street has access to expanded waste sorting (according to Nørrebro wastemodel), and the odd-numbered side has regular access to disposal of waste. Furthermore, examples of well-functional cases with expanded waste sorting in other municipalities are described.

RESULTS

Based on the interviews, the cases and the analysis, a list of recommendations for communication and information is issued to Miljøpunkt Nørrebro. This concludes which type(s) of information that could be the most appropriate way to inform citizen about "Den Talende Miljøstation" and waste sorting in general. The preferred category of information is based on instinct, meaning easy understandable and visually explained, with short description of further handling.

Figure 1 How to sort your waste correctly